

«The challenges of operational risk management in the Moroccan company: a literature review»

«Les enjeux de la gestion des risques opérationnels dans l'entreprise marocaine : Revue de littérature»

Received : 13 Février

Revisited: 15 Juin

Accepted : 4 Aout 2025

Classification JEL: G32

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Abstract

This document provides an overview of the main challenges facing operational risk management in Moroccan companies. It also lists the main sources of risk these institutions encounter, such as human, technical, and regulatory risks. The research also highlights gaps in risk identification, assessment, and management in the region, which can be seriously hampered by insufficient resources and low risk appetite, a lack of risk culture or also an inadequate regulatory regime. It also highlights the lack of a coherent strategy to systematically integrate risk management instruments into corporate governance. Given the specific economic and institutional conditions characterizing Morocco, this document proposes greater professionalization of operational risk management. Finally, it suggests avenues for research to further strengthen the capacity of Moroccan companies to anticipate, prevent, and effectively manage these risks in accordance with international best practices and sustainable development needs.

KEYWORDS: Risk, risk management, operational risks, Moroccan companies, challenges.

RESUMÉ

Dans cette revue, l'attention est concentrée sur les problèmes de gestion des risques opérationnels des entreprises marocaines. Elle identifie et discute les types de risques les plus rencontrés (humains, techniques, réglementaires), ainsi que les lacunes des méthodes actuelles d'identification, d'évaluation et de contrôle des risques. L'analyse démontre un manque de culture du risque et les difficultés liées au manque de ressources disponibles et à une structure réglementaire adaptée. Elle recommande une meilleure intégration des outils de gestion des risques dans les stratégies d'entreprise et souligne les directions de recherche qui pourraient être poursuivies dans le contexte économique et institutionnel marocain.

MOTS CLÉS : Risque, gestion des risques, risques opérationnels, entreprises marocaines, enjeux.

Introduction:

Moroccan companies are susceptible to challenges related to the increasing risks of globalization (OECD, 2016).

Despite the considerable efforts made by governments to support businesses, pillars of the national economy, the growing complexity and unpredictability of emerging risks (such as climate change, pandemics, cyberattacks, etc.) highlight the need for proactive and adaptive risk management (World Economic Forum, 2023). This situation is generating sustained interest from professionals, experts, analysts, managers, and policymakers in improving risk management strategies in the short and medium term (World Economic Forum, 2025).

Regardless of the company's role, risk is an essential part of its life cycle and, therefore, of its existence. So it's important to correctly understand its consequences, subject to slowing down the economic development of the organization (Regards croisés, 2023). Indeed, when companies have highly risky profiles and are faced with major crises, their survival, or even that of their sector of activity, is threatened. Otherwise, a rigorous risk management approach is essential (Alaoui, 2022). Large companies generally have a formalized risk culture at different levels: organizational, technical, legal, cultural, etc.

The study of risk management has undergone significant evolution in recent decades, integrating multidisciplinary approaches from the social sciences to geographical and financial disciplines. This progression is marked by the contribution of many actors, including researchers, professionals, and decision-makers. Benjamin Franklin, a pioneer in this field since the 18th century, underlines the importance of risk-taking for progress, mainly through his commitment to developing fire insurance. For the author, "There are many ways of failing, but the safest way is never to take risks" (Franklin, 1706). The company must, therefore, find a balance between the necessary risk and the risk that calls into question the organization's survival. In addition, (Joffre and Koenig, 1985) consider that companies must imperatively build a strategy integrating the financial and operational risks they face. These authors, among others, establish the foundations of a discipline that has become indispensable in different sectors. Therefore, risk management is not a recent concept. However, the occurrence of different events of a complex nature is changing risk management. These elements highlight the urgency and the need to control risks. This study analyzes Moroccan companies' operational risk management (ORM) practices in a complex and constantly changing economic context. These companies are faced with multidimensional challenges that can compromise their sustainability. From this perspective, it seems interesting to identify and analyze the challenges of the Moroccan company in terms of operational risk management. This study is organized around three parts: the first describes the theoretical framework on operational risk, the second presents operational risk management (ORM), the system and the management to be mobilized by Moroccan companies, and the third part addresses the different challenges related to operational risks for Moroccan companies.

Part I: The conceptual model of operational risk

1. The notion of risk

The term risk comes from the Italian *risico* or *rischio*, which is derived from the classical Arabic *rizq*. The concept describes the occurrence of possible damage.

The use of the term risk is directly related to danger or vulnerability. However, the danger is associated with the Probability of deterioration or nuisance (Pesqueux, 2024). The analysis of the concepts of risk and danger suggests a causal relationship. The concept of risk has undergone a remarkable evolution over the centuries, particularly with the occurrence of disasters, crises, and financial scandals, with additional costs as a corollary. Therefore, the use of the term risk is frequent in different disciplines, thus highlighting the need to present the various definitions to frame the term in its entirety.

(Knight & Jones, 2002), Note, in this sense, the difference between risk and uncertainty. The authors define risk as a decision-making context in which the possibility and Probability of the risk occurring are known.

(Markowitz, 1991) equates risk in financial activity with the variance of returns, thus considering investment to be dependent on fluctuations in future returns.

In another register, (Douglas & Wildavsky, 1982) consider risk a social concept that varies according to cultures and social environments. For (Kessler, 2002), risk results from the evolution or innovation of technical and industrial tools. From these few definitions of risk, a multiplicity of meanings emerges depending on the perception and the discipline that apprehends it (from statistics, economics, sociology, and anthropology).

(Darsa, 2016) for his part, puts forward a fundamental reflection. Although the company is exposed to many risks that can negatively impact its sustainability, namely economic and financial costs, it is important to identify the different families of risks. This identification is crucial for the survival of any company. The author thus distinguishes thirteen classes of risks that he groups in a three-dimensional pyramid. The first dimension encompasses the different themes. The second dimension extends from the individual to the group of people. The third dimension is linked to the company's environment (at the macroeconomic or microeconomic level).

Figure 1: Risk pyramid

Source :(Darsa, 2016)

The thirteen classes of risks are omnipresent and can negatively affect the company's continuity and performance. Adequate and powerful risk management is essential to ensure the company's sustainability.

2. Transition from risk to risk management

Following the multiple bankruptcies and accounting frauds, not to mention the 2007-2008 premium crisis, risk management is essential. It involves observing several essential steps, including risk identification and assessment.

Figure 2: Risk management process

Source : (Kermisch, 2012)

The risk identification stage is crucial for project implementation and constitutes a key stage for its success. It consists of identifying the principal risks and the detailed analysis of the processes, the areas of vulnerability, and the possibilities of risk occurrence

(PIERANDREI, 2025). The risk assessment phase comes once the risks have been identified and qualified according to their Probability of occurrence and according to a criticality scale. This stage formalizes the risk by measuring it using two variables. The first is the Probability of occurrence over a given period, and the second corresponds to the criticality scale or impact.

$$\text{Risk assessment} = \text{Probability of occurrence} * \text{Criticality scale}$$

Source: Authors

This routing of risk towards risk management ensures the validity of decision-making, minimizes negative repercussions, and promotes anticipation (forecasts and probabilities).

3. Risk management

Risk management refers to a process that aims to identify, assess, and prioritize potential risks that could harm the company's existence.

According to (Robert S. Kaplan & Anette Mikes, 2012), there are three types of risks in this sense: avoidable risks, strategic risks, and external risks. The authors emphasize the importance of understanding each type of risk with personalized management. Douglas (W. Hubbard, 2020) favors quantitative modeling over traditional risk management methods. The international standard (ISO 31000, 2018) considers risk management as "coordinated activities to direct and steer an organization in terms of risk."

These different perceptions reveal that the concept of risk management has a comprehensive meaning but requires a rational, functional, determined, and concrete orientation (Georges Dionne, 2013). In this context, pursuing a risk management policy that allows both corrective actions to be taken and capitalizing on the occurrence of the risk proves to be judicious (Georges Dionne, 2013). This harmonious combination is achievable by mastering the four risk management strategies to preserve the company's strategic, organizational, regulatory, and financial interests (ALAOUI & DHIBA, 2022).

4. Risk management strategies

Risk management strategies can be merged depending on the typology of the risk encountered. The four strategies aim to provide coverage against the risk (ALAOUI & DHIBA, 2022). In the event of an occurrence, business leaders must choose a strategy that offers an opportunity to maximize profit in a changing and complex environment (Jean-Paul Louisot, 2016). These four structured strategies promoting the treatment of the Probability of risk and the reduction of negative repercussions can be represented in this Figure 3:

Figure 3: Risk management strategies

Source: Authors

The event's occurrence is the fine line between avoidance, prevention, acceptance, and transfer strategies. To move away from risk, the company often opts for the avoidance strategy by changing or abandoning the activities that generate the risk through liquidation or sale and sometimes even by reallocating and redefining strategic plans. This approach eliminates operations, transactions, and risky sources (Pierandrei, 2019). In an uncertain environment, the choice of prevention consists of facing risks by anticipating them to reduce the Probability of their occurrence (Pierandrei, 2019). This is done through internal control systems, mapping, scenario analysis, etc.

On the other hand, when a risky event occurs, two strategies emerge. The first corresponds to acceptance. In this context, various crisis management modalities and plans occur, such as provisioning, distribution, separation of activities, and even subcontracting. The second refers to the transfer, generally reallocating the risk to another party and insurance to protect against losses and damages (Pierandrei, 2019). These strategies make it possible to deal with the different risks in a structured and thoughtful manner.

Part II: Operational risk management: System and management

1. Operational risk management

The Basel Committee (2003) defines operational risk as a potential loss linked to human error, an unexpected external event, or resulting from an incompatible and failing internal system. (IBM, 2021) agrees with the definition of risk management put forward by (PIERANDREI, 2025) which highlights the different steps to be observed to minimize the Probability of the risk occurring and its negative repercussions. From this perspective, the

international standard (ISO 31000, 2018) raises awareness among organizations about operational risk management, identifying, assessing, and treating risks to reduce the negative repercussions on the company. These different meanings emphasize the control of processes to guarantee a company's continuity, performance, and sustainability by ensuring relevant risk management while reducing the most problematic risks.

2. Typologies of operational risk

The Basel Committee (2003), in ensuring the monitoring and supervision of the balance of the global financial system, identifies seven categories of operational risk. It thus distinguishes internal fraud involving employees or managers within an organization or company, external fraud, and the inadequacy of internal human resources and workplace security practices. This also includes customers, products, and business practices that concern inadequacies via professional obligations towards customers or product specificities. This also includes damage to physical assets, business interruption, and the malfunction of processing processes relating to errors in execution, order placement, delivery, or the relationship with suppliers and salespeople. Companies must control these typologies cited, which cover various operational risks, to ensure stability and safety of execution. (Lamarque & Maurer 2009) focus on assessing and managing operational risks. They consider the traditional quantitative approach insufficient for controlling these risk typologies and suggest merging quantitative and qualitative approaches to preserve the daily functioning of the activity, hence the importance given to the following paragraph.

3. Operational risk devices

Establishing operational risk systems is part of a program to industrialize operational risk management. This program requires the involvement of all parties for its implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and continuous improvement. Its implementation involves adopting two essential approaches: a qualitative approach and a quantitative one.

3.1 Qualitative approaches

Qualitative approaches provide several tools for operational risk management in Moroccan companies, as mentioned below.

a. The internal incident management system

It consists of using an internal platform for the collection, management, and analysis of incidents within the company. This system includes some specificities, such as the definition of each person's roles and responsibilities in the collection and detection of incidents, as well as the identification of the threshold and extent of incidents. This system is based on assessment techniques and reactive and agile approaches to trigger alarm signals according to their urgency.

b. The external incident management system

Exposure to risk and exceptional events is an inevitable reality in a company's life cycle. However, this accumulation of experience is limited. This justifies the need to use external databases, referring to the experience of different companies based on data collected from several references (annual reports, regulatory bodies, press articles).

c. The establishment of risk indicators-KRI

As mentioned above, the company is exposed to high risk, constantly evolving (Oble et al., 2019). Having specific tools to anticipate the occurrence of risk accompanied by an effective alert system is essential for frequent assessment. These tools promote better decision-making provided specific criteria are met, such as reliability, frequency, relevance, and importance. Monitoring and assessing risks in different areas vary depending on the sector, activity, and specific requirements of the company. Here are some risk indicators represented in the following table:

Table 1 : Indicators according to risk category

Risk Category	KRI	Description
Operational	Defect ratio = Number of defects / \sum Number operations*100	Monitoring the quality of operations to take corrective measures and reduce the company's defect rate.
	Repair ratio = Number of repairs / \sum Number of failures *100	Monitoring the performance of the company's maintenance teams.
Compliance	Compliance ratio = Number of compliances / \sum Number of operations*100	Monitoring the quality of company operations.
	Safety compliance rate = Number of safety compliances / \sum Number of operations*100	Monitoring the quality of security operations

Financial	$\text{Solvency ratio} = \frac{\text{Equity}}{\text{total liabilities}} * 100$	Assessment of the financial stability of the company.
	$\text{Debt ratio} = \frac{\text{Total debt}}{\text{equity}} * 100$	Evaluation of the financing of the activity by using the company's funds.
	$\text{Profitability ratio} = \frac{\text{Net income}}{\text{Equity}} * 100$	Evaluation of the profitability of the company's investments.
Reputation	$\text{Customer loyalty ratio} = \frac{\text{Number of final loyal customers}}{\sum \text{Number of initial customers}}$	Evaluation of the company's customer satisfaction.
	$\text{Awareness ratio} = \frac{\text{Number of PRs aware of the company}}{\sum \text{Number of PRs in the target population}} * 100$	Assessing the impact of corporate reputation.
Computer science	$\text{Cyber attacks ratio} = \frac{\text{Number of cyber attacks}}{\sum \text{Number of IT assets}} * 100$	Quantifying the level of risk of vulnerability to IT threats in the company

Source : Auteurs

d. Control devices

In this regard, it is important to refer to the Management theory (Fayol, 1999), which highlights the importance of adopting and adapting actions to achieve the objectives set. (Henri-Pierre Maders & Jean-Luc Masselin, 2015) subdivide the concept of control into three types. The first level is permanent type control, which is done either manually or automatically by the processes put in place. The internal control function triggers the second level of control, and finally, the third level of periodic control concerns audit and inspection. These controls pursue the main objective of securing the activity. In this context, the control deals with identifying anomalies and potential incidents to minimize their occurrence. It also integrates the distribution of responsibilities, securing the activity, and optimizing the system

e. Risk mapping

According to de (Mareschal, 2003), risk mapping is an essential tool that helps avoid threatening and worrying situations. Risk mapping thus aims to identify, qualify, prioritize, and treat the different risks that the company is likely to face.

At the same time, its properties facilitate the representation and prioritization of risks and the situation at a specific time. As such, mapping represents a strategic management tool and a communication instrument that allows the manager to make decisions.

f. Scenario analysis

(Kahn, Herman & Anthony J. Weiner, 1967) Describe the events and situations likely to impact the company's macro system. To do this, the authors evaluate the results and the possible repercussions, as well as their probabilities of occurrence and their degree of criticality. In this sense, they use different qualitative and/or quantitative methods concerning this approach. The analysis of scenarios makes it possible to design and verify theoretical situations that can weaken the strategic orientations, the results, or even the company's sustainability.

3.2. Quantitative approaches

According to Directive 2009/138/EC, Solvency II, which establishes the framework for the rules applicable to insurance companies within the European Union and in Morocco, there are two approaches to quantifying risks.

The first is the Standard Formula approach (Basel Committee, 2018), which aims to provide coverage against operational risks. Regulators designed it to assess capital requirements by applying fixed coefficients in addition to pre-established risk classes. It allows for simple applications. However, it does not express the different specificities of a company's risks.

The second approach is the Internal Model (Basel Committee, 2018). It offers a perspective for the company to develop and use unique models to assess its capital requirements in relation to its own funds. The advantage of this model is its adjustable and precise nature. However, it requires validation from regulators and the obligation to provide detailed data.

These two approaches help Moroccan companies better understand and manage their operational risks. The decision to opt between the two approaches is conditioned by the abundance of resources, regulatory obligations, and difficulties encountered by Moroccan companies in carrying out their activities (ALAOUI & DHIBA, 2022).

4. The establishment of operational risk management

To enable the Moroccan company to monitor, analyze, make strategic decisions, and monitor its regular activity, it must use several tools to manage its operational risk.

The first tool relates to the dashboard (TDB), which is presented as a synthetic and solid tool that brings together all the effective and efficient indicators to help with decision-making. (Stephan, 2006) believes that the interest of TDBs lies in improving arbitration in certain situations. Thanks to visual and dynamic elements, it allows data to be visualized and read quickly and efficiently while ensuring instant monitoring.

Another tool is monitoring action plans, which is essential for managing operational risks and improving the situation the company faces. (Drucker, 2010) presents a "management by objectives" (MPO) approach that involves several stages. This includes identifying and assessing risks, developing actions to control them, assigning these actions to specific people, monitoring deadlines, carrying out controls, and continuously adapting the action plan.

Furthermore, the Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) approach (Lam, 2003) combines several processes for identifying, quantifying, and managing the risks the Moroccan company must face to achieve its strategic objectives. Two variables must be considered: losses and possibly the costs of prevention and protection against risk. (Lam, 2003) emphasizes the different tools and processes that make finding neutrality between performance and risk possible.

In another register, the business continuity plan (BCP) (Darsa, 2016) plays a crucial role for any company wishing to ensure the continuity of its activity and maintain the organization's operational conditions. It is analyzed as an immediate formal response to a degraded situation.

The last tool refers to insurance, which corresponds, according to (Hémard, 1924), to an act of commitment that allows the subscriber to cover his financial losses in the face of an operational risk resulting from internal dysfunctions. The objective is to ensure financial balance, cost reduction, and process optimization. It is, therefore, a steering tool or a complementary lever to counter operational risks.

Regardless of the Moroccan company's size, an effective ORM through this range of steering devices and tools can generate beneficial results. This is reflected in particular by the reduction of losses, the improvement of efficiency, the strengthening of compliance and trust, the development of risk culture, the creation of a competitive advantage, and the optimization of decision-making. However, the Moroccan company must meet specific challenges in managing operational risks.

Part III: Issues related to operational risk management in Moroccan companies

1. The challenges of operational risk management

The multiplicity of issues in operational risk management in Moroccan companies has significant consequences at several levels. Moroccan companies must integrate them to maintain their organization's stability and resilience.

2. Types of operational risk management issues

The Moroccan company's major concern is its financial stake, the improvement of its performance, the minimization of its losses, and the optimization of its costs. (Christian Jimenez, et al., 2008) Note that good activity management, the improvement of processes like the establishment of a solid ORM system, the optimization of equity, and compliance with regulatory requirements improve financial performance.

In this same perspective, proactive management of operational risks promotes the reduction of losses resulting from system malfunctions or process inadequacies (Crouhy et al., 2000). (Lam, 2003) In this sense, the interest of a good ORM is to optimize costs related to direct, indirect, production, variable, marginal costs, etc., while avoiding potential losses and minimizing future expenses. However, the organizational issue represents the center of interest of all the issues of ORM since it combines all the interconnected parameters that ensure the survival of an organization. (Georges Dionne, 2013) It highlights the importance of integrating risk management into companies' decision-making processes through risk governance. This involves establishing internal models, namely control and standardized procedures, to manage financial&operational risks and reduce anomalies to improve efficiency.

Regulation, for its part, generates better performance and stability, representing an important GRO issue to improve transparency and corporate governance. The international standard (ISO 31000, 2018) affects the internal approaches and methods companies use to administer and manage their operational risks.

At the same time, at the national level, in addition to international standards, Moroccan companies are required to follow national regulators such as those of Bank al-Maghrib, the Moroccan market authority, the Insurance and Social Welfare Control Authority, or even the Ministry of Finance to set up specific ORM systems. The latter can also impose or promote training programs for risk managers to make them aware of risks for better management practices. (Jean-Michel Pottier, 2023) Emphasizes, in this way, the importance of producing regular reports in order to increase the level of transparency and accountability.

Another regulatory dimension presented by (Christian Jimenez et al., 2008) consists of carrying out internal and external audit missions to evaluate ORM systems. Finally, the strategic issue is inevitable for any company concerned about its ORM to avoid failure in all areas. According to (Pignault & Magne, 2014), the first strategic key refers to security and continuity of operations by identifying the various risks that harm them. (Huberson & Vraie, 2015) Mention business continuity plans and the emergency plan that provides corrective measures to ensure continuity of operations and mitigate interruptions.

The second strategic key concerns the company's reputation. For (Chapelle, 2020), damage to the company's image is analyzed as a high operational risk, and therefore, good management of the reputation dimension can trigger trust in the entire ecosystem of the company with considerable financial profits. In the Moroccan context, several companies have been affected by reputational damage with devastating consequences over the last decade. Still, at the level of strategic issues, it seems helpful to indicate that an adequate ORM can trigger a competitive advantage. (Porter, 1985) assimilates this dimension into an asset for the company to surpass its competitors and stand out through the different techniques and current approaches.

3. Methodology:

The approach to this research involves clearly defined key steps. First, this study is based on an exploration of the keywords "risks"; "risk management"; "risk management, operational risk - Moroccan companies" "risk management challenges" After clearly defining the subject of these objectives and keywords, it is crucial to begin a systematic literature search by consulting bibliographic databases such as Science Direct, Cairinfo, Moroccan journals... between 2000 and 2023 this identification step allowed us to select 780 articles with an initial screening including 540 exclusions including 220 duplicates, 230 off-topic. Then, another criterion was added that of eligibility with 240 remaining studies examined, of which 165 were excluded due to the absence of Moroccan empirical data (85), insufficient methodological quality (50) and thematic redundancy (30), to finally settle on 75 included studies. The selection criteria are aligned with the implementation of Basel III. A more in-depth focus was established on empirical studies, sectoral reports and research carried out according to the Moroccan context.

Figure 4: Prisma diagram

Source : Authors

4. Results and discussions:

At the national level, various initiatives have taken place to rehabilitate the operational risk management structure, however, many gaps persist, for example on the cultural level. On the one hand, there is a vertical command or, in other words, a verticality of power leading to a suppression of warning signals, which leads to a concentration of decisions at the upper level, especially in emerging economies, the case of Morocco, conveyed in the phenomenon of "power distance" according to (Hofstede et al., 2010). On the other hand, (AUSIM & DATA PROTECT, 2018) highlights that the corporate culture is not very aware of IT risks, reflecting the lack of commitment from management. In this same perspective, the study by (France Milleken & Morisson, 2003) conducts an exploratory analysis on the reasons why employees filter critical or negative information in the middle levels and conceptualizes "culture of silence". In this same sense (Mialed, 2020) highlights the importance of the GRO culture which can lead to considerable performance and proposes indicators to measure the risk management culture. Then on the economic level, the costs linked to operational risks significantly reduce the financial, economic and commercial performance of companies according to a study (Bari, 2016) which leads to underinvestment in risk management tools of Moroccan companies. Furthermore (Chemlal et al., 2017) highlight according to a survey of 112 Moroccan SMEs that risk management mechanisms are informal and unsuitable for dealing with economic crises. In another register, the regulation of the banking sector contributes to operational performance in the banking sector in terms of compliance according to the prudential approach (Mchich & Amraoui, 2024). On the other hand, the general regulatory framework in Morocco is framed by legal texts such as law 17-95 of the commercial code stipulating the obligation to set up internal control, law 31-08 for SAs which require audit committees and risk reporting and law 12-18 on cybersecurity (2021) specifies the mandatory notification of cyber incidents as well as law 03-20 focused on strengthening the governance, supervision and risk management framework including operational risk. However, it noted the absence of a unified framework dedicated to operational risk whose obligations are fragmented by sector unlike the banking sector. Regarding the IT issue, according to (BELHAJ et al., 2024) estimates the inadequacy of tools linked to IT system mapping, audits and risk matrix. Concomitantly, (Chemlal et al., 2017) emphasize that SMEs do not have a formal budget dedicated to risk management. Finally, on the human level (Mchich & Amraoui, 2024) emphasize the link between IT risk management, performance, and the importance of qualified human capital, hence the importance of the training dimension. To go further from the aforementioned gaps, major permanent implications are summarized in the loss of competitiveness on an international scale, especially in export sectors. Beyond a superficial description of the challenges of operational risk management, it is important to highlight these challenges in the Moroccan context, accompanied by the root causes of these challenges and their implications and impacts on the national sphere.

Table 2: Challenges and effects of operational risk management in Moroccan companies

Key Issue	Occurrence	Causes	Effects
Regulatory compliance	Illegal adoption of Basel III (banking and non-banking sectors);	High implementation costs; Lack of local expertise in advanced modeling;	Sectoral dualism: Banks are over-controlled, SMEs under-regulated;
Cyber Risks	58% of Moroccan companies state the increase in cyber attacks as the main risk, compared to 29% reported in the last study (Allianz, 2025)	Accelerated digitalization without dedicated security budgets; Lack of a cybersecurity culture;	Modernization amplifies vulnerabilities in local businesses;
Governance & Culture	Centralization of risk decisions (BKAM, 2025) A verticality of power "power distance" (Hofstede et al., 2010) (France Milleken & Morisson, 2003)	Hierarchical organizational structure	Limited resilience: Low responsiveness to external crises (e.g. COVID-19)
Human Risks	High turnover leading to knowledge loss. Insufficient formalization (Yassafi, 2016)	Continuing education deficit Ineffective retention policies	Impact of informal relationships on process continuity

Source : Authors

The analysis of the state of operational risk management reveals that the Moroccan landscape requires an upgrade of regulatory, cultural, organizational and economic aspects by aligning with international standards and practices. All of the issues cited require actions to mitigate these challenges through the regulatory expansion of risks, including operational risks, or even by creating a simplified operational risk framework for companies that are now the economic fabric of the country. Then, national and international institutions and public policies are beginning to organize themselves to pursue a gradual integration into a structured management logic for Moroccan

companies, which remains for the moment not legally binding. At the same time, the state effort is illustrated by subsidies for the benefit of Moroccan companies, and more particularly exporting SMEs, in terms of auditing operational risk management to enhance their international competitiveness and align with CSR and international standards. Strengthening risk culture through training programs that must be mandatory on operational risks in OFPPT programs and universities, moreover these companies can benefit from free e-learning modules adapted to the agri-food, textile and construction sectors. Another course of action can be proposed on the basis of the report (World Bank, 2003) "Promoting Agro-Entreprise and agro-Food Systems Development in developing and transitions countries" published by the World Bank examines among other things effective strategies to promote and strengthen risk management related to agricultural activities, policies, logistics etc. The major objective is to pool resources between small businesses and adopt the cluster approach or SME associations to reduce costs, pool expertise and have access to financial instruments and market information, in other words, to have a pooled risk management expert for ten SMEs.

Table 3 : Operational risk management action plan and expected results

Action plan	Expected results
Regulatory upgrade	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Better shock absorption; -Systematized risk mapping; -Implementation of real-time monitoring systems; -Improved financial ratings; -Alignment with standards (Basel, ISO, etc.)
Popularized training and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Collective risk awareness; -Team empowerment; -Reduction of human errors; -Adaptation to visual tools;
Pooling of experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sharing of expert costs; - Access to specialized expertise - Creation of sectoral incident databases and promotion of the sharing of best practices

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of tools adapted to the national context; - Creation of crisis units for optimal management of systemic shocks.
State subsidies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boosting the risk maturity of Moroccan companies; - Technological modernization; - Inter-company synergy and structuring financing.

Source : Authors

This range of solutions is considered as regulatory, cultural, and economic levers for realistic implementation in the Moroccan context. The joint effort of the public and private sectors to rehabilitate and modernize operational risk management in Moroccan companies is rapidly expanding internationally. As a result, strengthening can result in the sharing of best practices and sectoral databases that promote active anticipation of the occurrence of inherent risks. Furthermore, it is essential to encourage academic research on operational risk management to expand and strengthen knowledge and provide appropriate solutions while strengthening the national academic climate and transferring this knowledge for practical purposes within companies.

In conclusion, operational risk management remains fragmented between a regulated banking sector and the economic fabric of Moroccan companies, generally consisting of SMEs and industries where a risk culture is gradually developing. Therefore, all stakeholders have an interest in pursuing an approach that is conscious, concrete, dynamic, and objective.

4.1. Methodological Limitations:

Through this research, the Moroccan research landscape reflects a lack of independent empirical publications on Moroccan companies and an overrepresentation of the banking sector, the majority of which are concentrated in the Casablanca and Rabat regions, targeting large companies with easy access to banking services. However, there is a neglect of companies, particularly data on small and medium-sized enterprises and their access to financing, as well as an underrepresentation of the issues in vulnerable regions. Furthermore, it should be noted that the informal sector and peripheral regions are excluded from the studies, constituting a representativeness bias since they cover a significant portion of Moroccan GDP. In another vein, there is a heterogeneity of definitions with conceptual variations in operational risk between the different existing studies. However, it is important to mention the dominance of sources from institutional entities, with an underestimation of criticism of the regulatory framework. Finally, the existence of opacity in Moroccan data due to the absence of a national registry of

operational incidents and, on the other hand, underreporting of fraud and cyberattacks to avoid reputational risks.

Conclusion and future outlook:

The goal of every business, from its inception, has been to create value, innovate, and seize opportunities. Consequently, zero risk does not exist. Uncertainty and danger are a daily part of the business and its components' economic activity. Therefore, recognizing this phenomenon is reflected in risk awareness and management.

The Moroccan economic fabric is heavily dominated by small and medium-sized enterprises, which account for a significant share of employment in terms of job creation as well as national production in terms of GDP. The government provides numerous forms of assistance through support programs, subsidies, the "INTELAKA" program, economic reforms, free trade agreements, and sectoral strategies, among other things. This support facilitates access to financing, encourages entrepreneurship, strengthens innovation and competitiveness, promotes socioeconomic integration, and increases added value. This support, beyond mere guidance, aims to preserve the survival and sustainability of businesses in the face of multiple existing risks. In this sense, greater efforts must be made and relevant solutions identified to ensure the survival of Moroccan businesses.

In this perspective, the ORM aspect is critical for Moroccan businesses, regardless of their size and scope, in a restrictive global economic sphere. However, as mentioned, an effective ORM approach and a robust system can improve business performance across various dimensions and prevent financial losses while overcoming the multitude of issues and challenges. This study revealed the absence of a single, specific regulatory framework that governs operational risk, compared to simple, effective practices within businesses. However, a patchwork of regulatory texts and best practices address aspects of operational risk. The research highlights the various challenges of operational risk management in Moroccan companies, highlighting the crucial nature of expanding regulatory frameworks for risks, including operational risks, and creating an operational risk framework, as well as promoting training and awareness to foster organizational culture with a view to mitigating the challenges of operational risk management.

Admittedly, the methodical approach, as mentioned, raises some biases. This study, which presents an in-depth documentary analysis highlighting some methodological limitations, raises the interest of supplementing this research with a future empirical study that will allow for a connection with stakeholders in Moroccan companies, particularly SMEs. This point will lead to a subsequent publication.

Furthermore, future scientific studies and knowledge production should be based on the identified gaps to address sectoral and geographic shortcomings outside of banking. Comparative and cross-sectional studies between SMEs and large companies, as well as Maghreb benchmarking studies, are also necessary. Similarly, it is important to thoroughly study the cultural impact. Additionally, the identification of new, yet unidentified threats is being considered, while creating a national operational risk

observatory with anonymized access for companies and finding digital solutions through the integration of artificial intelligence. These recommendations aim to revisit the identified limitations and gaps and provide a real lever for standardized research to strengthen the economic resilience of Moroccan companies. Therefore, several questions remain: How can we promote a shared operational risk culture and implement effective regulations in a changing and complex organizational context? And what is the impact of operational risk management on the financial performance of Moroccan companies?

Ultimately, the allocation of material, human, and financial resources represents the preliminary phase of good operational risk management. Once resources are allocated, Moroccan companies are able to address various operational risks by adopting good management practices, namely risk identification and assessment, control, monitoring, follow-up, and finally, strengthening the risk culture. However, its effectiveness depends primarily on the organizational culture and regulatory framework.

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